
Stem Bark Essential Oil Composition of *Schefflera quangtriensis* C. B. Shang

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Abstract The essential oil extracted from the stem bark of *Schefflera quangtriensis* (C. B. Shang) was prepared by steam distillation of fresh materials in a glass for 3 hours. The essential oil yields were 0.02% from the stem bark. The essential oil from the stem bark of *Schefflera quangtriensis* analyzed by GC/MS consists of 43 constituents identified accounting 97.7% of the oil. The major components of the essential oil from the stem bark of *Schefflera quangtriensis* are (*E*)-Caryophyllene (21.3%), δ -Cadinene (14.1%), α -Copaene (9.2%), Limonene (7.9%), α -Humulene (6.8%), α -Cubebene (5.7%).

Keywords *Schefflera quangtriensis*, Araliaceae, Essential oil

Introduction

The genus *Schefflera* is the largest genus of the Araliaceae family, consisting about 1100 species distributed in tropical and sub-tropical regions [1] and 50 species and 4 varieties of which found in Vietnam [2]. Species of this genus have been used in folk medicine for the treatment of stomachache, rheumatic arthritis, and made for vegetable [3,4]. The chemical composition from the essential oil of different species of the genus *Schefflera* has been reported. The major constituents of *S. stellata*, *S. heptaphylla*, *S. myriocarpa* were found as β -pinene, α -phellandrene, limonene, methyl eugenol, β -Caryophyllene, α -humulene, germacrene D, germacrene B, and epi- α -cadinol [5,6,7]. *Schefflera quangtriensis* (C.B. Shang) is an endemic tree in Vietnam and threatened by habitat loss [8,2]. The chemical composition from the essential oil of stem bark of this plant has not been studied. In this paper, we report the chemical composition of essential oil from the stem bark of *Schefflera quangtriensis*.

Materials and methods

Plant Materials

The stem bark of *S. quangtriensis* was collected from Bac Huong Hoa Natural Reserve, Quang Tri Province, Vietnam in July 2016. The species was identified by Msc. Nguyen Van Dat at Vietnam National Museum of Nature and a voucher specimen DAT-01 was deposited at the herbarium of the Vietnam National Museum of Nature (VNMN), Vietnam.

Extraction of essential oil

About 1000g of the fresh stem bark of *S. quangtriensis* was used for extraction of the essential oil. The essential oil was extracted by hydrodistillation using a Clevenger-type apparatus for 3 hours according to the Vietnam Pharmacopoeia method [9]. The obtained oil was yellowish with characteristic odor and then dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 and stored in darkness at 5°C until the time of analysis. The yield of oil was 0.02% (v/w).

Analysis of the volatile oil

Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometer (GC-MS) analysis of the essential oil of *S. quangtriensis* was employed a Thermo Scientific Trace 1310 coupled with mass spectrometry Thermo Scientific ITQ 900 equipped with capillary column TG-5MS (30 m x 0.25 mm i.d, 0,25 μ m film thickness). The oven temperature was held at 40°C, then programmed to 240°C (hold 5min) at a rate of 4°C/min. Helium was used as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min. The injector temperature was 250°C, and the injection volume of 0.1 mL in *n*-hexane, with a split ratio of 1:60. The mass spectra (MS) were operated in electron impact mode (70 eV), and the MS data were acquired in scan mode with a mass range of *m/z* 40 - 400.

Identification of the Constituents

The peaks were quantified by calculating the percentage of the peak area of each component by comparison to the sum of the peaks of other compounds. The identification of the components was made on the basis of retention index (RI, determined with reference to a homologous series of *n*-alkanes C₈-C₂₀, under identical experimental conditions), MS library search (NIST 14 version 2.2) and by comparing with MS literature data [10].

Results and discussion

Forty-three compounds were identified according to their mass spectra and their relative retention indices determined in a non-polar stationary phase capillary column, comprising 97.7% of the total oil constituents. The identified compounds are listed in Table 1 in elution order from the TG-5 column, along with the percentage composition determined using GC-MS of each component and its retention index. The major constituents of the essential oil were (*E*)-Caryophyllene (21.3%) and δ -Cadinene (14.1%). The other minor constituents were α -Copaene (9.2%), Limonene (7.9%), α -Humulene (6.8%), α -Cubebene (5.7%). The oil was found to be rich in sesquiterpene hydrocarbons (87.2%), residual was monoterpene hydrocarbons (10.6%).

Table 1: The chemical composition of essential oil from the stem bark of *Schefflera quangtriensis*

No.	Components	RI	Percentage (%)
1	α -Thujene	933	1.4
2	β -Pinene	976	0.2
3	Myrcene	991	0.1
4	<i>o</i> -Cymene	1024	0.2
5	Limonene	1029	7.9
6	1,8-Cineole	1031	0.4
7	Myrtenol	1191	0.4
8	α -Cubebene	1353	5.7
9	α -Copaene	1379	9.2
10	iso-Longifolene	1393	3.9
11	α -Gurjunene	1413	0.6
12	(<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene	1423	21.3
13	β -Gurjunene	1433	0.2
14	Aromadendrene	1443	0.1
15	α -Humulene	1458	6.8
16	9-epi-(<i>E</i>)-Caryophyllene	1467	2.3
17	trans-Cadina-1(6),4-diene	1477	0.5
18	Amorpha-4,7(11)-diene	1485	1.7
19	γ -Patchoulene	1500	2.2
20	α -Bulnesene	1510	0.3
21	Butylated hydroxytoluene	1515	1.0
22	γ -Cadinene	1518	0.6

23	δ -Cadinene	1527	14.1
24	trans-Cadina-1,4-diene	1536	0.4
25	α -Calacorene	1547	0.5
26	Silphiperfol-5-en-3-ol A	1554	0.7
27	Germacrene B	1565	1.5
28	Caryophyllenyl alcohol	1571	0.3
29	Spathulenol	1582	0.3
30	β -Copaen-4- α -ol	1588	2.2
31	Ledol	1600	1.0
32	Khusimone	1606	3.2
33	β -Biotol	1614	0.7
34	α -Corocalene	1626	0.1
35	1-epi-Cubenol	1633	1.3
36	α -Muurolol	1646	1.6
37	Valerianol	1659	1.6
38	trans-Calamenen-10-ol	1671	0.3
39	Germacra-4(15),5,10(14)-trien-1- α -ol	1683	0.2
40	11- α H-Himachal-4-en-1- β -ol	1700	0.3
41	Longifolol	1715	0.1
42	(Z)-Nuciferol	1722	0.3
43	γ -Costol	1743	0.1
44	Monoterpene hydrocarbons		10.6
45	Sesquiterpene hydrocarbons		87.2
46	Total Identified		97.7

RI: Retention indices relative to C₈ - C₂₀ n-alkanes on TG-5MS capillary column

Conclusion

This is the first report on the chemical constituents of the essential oil of *S. quangtriensis*. The compounds (*E*)-Caryophyllene (21.3%), δ -Cadinene (14.1%), α -Copaene (9.2%), Limonene (7.9%), α -Humulene (6.8%) and α -Cubebene (5.7%) were major constituents in the stem bark. Further studies are required to investigate the biological activities of the essential oil constituents of this plant.

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